

THE ROLE OF YOUTH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATION ACTIVITIES AND DIGITAL ECONOMY IN OUR COUNTRY

¹Sadullaeva Sh.A., ²Abdulazizova Sh.A.

¹Joint Belarusian-Uzbek Institute of Intersectoral Practical Technical Qualifications in Tashkent, Deputy Director, Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, Professor

²Joint Belarusian-Uzbek Institute of Intersectoral Practical Technical Qualifications in Tashkent, Researcher

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that in our country, young people and their abilities, knowledge and skills have become the main factor in the well-being of any society and the economic development of the state. Today in Uzbekistan, human capital, without a doubt, is a priority area in social and economic policy. The development of human capital is a prerequisite for the development of an innovative economy, a knowledge of economy, investments, global information systems, the latest technologies and new forms of business. The issue of human capital occupies one of the main places in connection with the implementation of the tasks defined in the strategic development programs adopted by the state and the regulatory framework, that is, solving the problems arising at the current stage of global development in Youth policy is one of the pressing issues.*

Keywords: *economy, investments, global information systems, the latest technologies and new forms of business.*

World experience and practice show that countries that have chosen investment in human capital as a priority to achieve high development. For example, in developed countries, much attention is paid to investing in the full cycle of education, that is, investing in the education and upbringing of young people from 3 to 22 years old. Training young people in the field of information technology is one of the most important means of improving country's economy and developing the digital economy. The political, economic and social changes that have occurred in the lives of the population of our country over the past 5-6 years, especially the opportunities provided to young people and the support of their activities in all aspects, serve as a vivid example. The above-mentioned ideas also include the formation of human capital, that is, the potential of young people in our country is reflected as the main criterion.

In recent years, our country has paid special attention to the development of science, technology and the creation of sufficient conditions for young people.

It is important to suggest that the current reforms and goals put forward during the transition to a new quality of development in Uzbekistan were clearly and repeatedly expressed at their level. The problem is how to implement these goals, prepare the country in practice, bring it to a new state and find mechanisms for transformation. Full-scale implementation of the planned strategic guidelines will create great opportunities for creative and, most importantly, effective work necessary for the new technological and knowledge-intensive economy of the country. But for this, the state, society and youth must clearly define their role in social and economic processes,

develop effective mechanisms for their participation in ensuring the national interests of the country.

"Working with young people, who make up almost half of the population of our country, will continue to be one of our main tasks," suggested the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev. At the same time, the task of systemic reform of science, changing target instructions and modernizing the mechanisms for its further development remains inevitable and relevant. In addition, our country faces the task of dynamic modernization of the entire system of socio-economic and socio-political relations, which will allow our country to strengthen its leading positions in the post-Soviet region and Central Asia. As a result of the change of generations, a simple or expanded repetition of the social structure is carried out, during this period the social essence of the activity of youth as a social group is revealed and its main social functions are demonstrated. When implementing large-scale reforms in our country, each new generation, thanks to its innovative potential, ensures the preservation of the integrity of society and participates in its improvement and change. In this way, both the development of youth and the reproduction of society are carried out.

Figure 1. Dynamics of changes in indicators of IT Park residents

At present time, acquiring professions in the field of information technology (IT) has become a trend not only in the world, but also among the youth of Uzbekistan. Because this industry is both modern and profitable. Over the past three years, attention to the development of information technology has increased significantly in Uzbekistan. As a result, the volume of services in the field has increased, and the education sector has expanded. For example, in 2021, residents of the IT Park provided services worth 2.5 trillion soums, while in 2022 this figure was 5 trillion soums. The volume of service exports in 2021 amounted to \$ 50 million, last year it reached \$ 140 million. That is, an increase of 2-3 times per year. As information technology develops, the demand for Uzbek programmers in the world market is growing.

Figure 2. Export volume of IT industry segments as of 2022 (thousand US dollars)

Definitely, there is a high shortage of IT personnel in the world, particularly in Uzbekistan. Because IT has penetrated almost all areas. Digitalization has become a need of the time. This means that there should be enough programmers for all networks. In this sense, it is necessary to

expand the use of digital technologies in the republic. Measures are being taken to ensure the effective use of IT services by all ministries and departments. This, in turn, helps to reduce unnecessary costs and the human factor.

Therefore, in order to develop the industry, first of all, it is necessary to teach it - education. Today, one of the most important issues is training the youth of Uzbekistan in information technology, creating conditions for their work and a market for their products. Therefore, the government pays special attention to the development of IT education.

Figure 3. Income of Uzbek freelancers from foreign platforms in 2022

The Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Digital Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan have begun to study modern software products for training engineers-technologists in such areas as construction, geology, mechanical engineering and transport. The IT Park and its branches will be connected to such universities, and teachers and students will be trained to work on new programs.

Today, young people who speak a foreign language receive additional income from abroad without leaving home through self-employment - freelancing. According to the Ministry of Digital Development, the number of self-employed people in the IT sector has grown to more than 70 thousand.

In 2022, freelancers from Uzbekistan transferred their income in the amount of \$ 11.8 million to Uzbekistan through money transfers or the Pioneers system. This is 7.4 times more than in 2019. That is, in 2019, the republic received 1.6 million dollars, in 2020 - 9.9 million dollars, in 2021 - 10.5 million dollars.

According to the analysis, IT certificates most often obtained by students are Data science (38%) and Full-stack development (27%) certificates. Currently, the most popular educational platforms in the IT field are QWASAR, Cisco, Oracle, Coursera, UDEMY, and it is on these platforms that young people receive online education.

Every year, new opportunities for supporting IT education appear in our country. If 3 years ago, only 11 IT training centers were residents of the IT Park, now more than 250 (20+ times)

educational centers enjoy benefits and opportunities created by our state. With the help of the IT Knowledge Fund (bilgi.uz), 30 billion soums were allocated to support educational centers, and preferential loans in the amount of 768 million soums were provided to 70 young people to cover their training costs.

** IT certificates are documents that confirm that you have the necessary knowledge and skills in the IT field (just like IELTS in English).*

Figure 4. *The most popular international IT certificates

Figure 5. The most popular international educational IT platforms

According to the information, over the past 5 years, 2 billion dollars (\$700 million in direct investment) have been directed to the IT sector of Uzbekistan. In particular, in 2022, the volume of investments in the ICT sector increased by 1.3 times, and the volume of services provided by

the industry increased by 1.25 times. As a result, ICT services per capita amounted to 621 thousand soums, and an additional 29.6 thousand people were employed.

Figure 6. Analysis of general indicators of educational residents

Figure 7. Dynamics of growth in the number of companies with foreign capital participation (by quarters as of 2022)

As a result of the improvement of the IT infrastructure and the creation of a favorable environment for foreign companies in Uzbekistan, the number of foreign IT companies operating in 2021 reached 23, and in 2022 - 157. At the end of last year, the number of residents of the IT Park was 1,037 people. The fact that IT companies in the country were granted a number of benefits contributes to their significant increase in number. In particular, such companies are exempt from social tax. They pay personal income tax at a rate of 7.5 percent. In addition, they will not be charged customs duties for the import of software not produced in Uzbekistan.

The role of international cooperation in supporting young people interested in this area is effective. Prestigious foreign organizations are investing in Uzbekistan. In particular, the UN Development Program grant of \$121,000 to support youth for the development of the digital economy, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe grant of \$145,000 to create training materials for training personnel in the open economy. The grant for data and training of

young people is one of them. It is believed that \$1 billion allocated by the World Bank will give a big boost to the development of the country's IT sector.

Figure 8. Uzbekistan's position in 2022 in international digitalization rankings

In the international rankings of 2022, Uzbekistan's position in the field of digitalization has improved significantly. In particular, according to the World Bank's GovTech Enablers Index, our country has grown by 65 points compared to 2020 in digital skills and innovation in public services. According to the GovTech Maturity Index, the public services sector has risen 37 places and entered Group A of leading countries in digital transformation among 198 countries. According to the 2022 e-government study conducted by the UN every two years, Uzbekistan has risen 18 places and entered the group of "highly, very highly developing" countries. In general, significant results have been achieved in the IT field in a short period of time. Efforts are being made to further develop the industry. Many experts suggest that Uzbekistan has sufficient potential for the development of this sector. This is due to the fact that more than half of the country's population is young people. And IT is rather a profession for young people.

In general, the number of people wishing to start their own business among the population and, above all, among young people, is increasing significantly. But most young people who are willing to take risks to improve their well-being currently have limited financial resources to do so. Entrepreneurship as a type of activity continues to be perceived negatively in society in some situations. At the same time, modern young people have a different attitude to commercial activities, viewing it as an opportunity for independence and decent income.

Besides that, the idea of forming an intellectual nation based on innovative development in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the most systematic initiatives of the head of our country. This highlights three main aspects of the formation of an intellectual nation in our country: the development of the education system, the development of science and the increase in the scientific potential of the country, the development of an innovative system. The type of highly developed, information society that our country strives for is characterized by the widespread introduction of

new information and scientific technologies, the development and growth of the knowledge industry.

By summarizing it should be suggested that education is a priority value and has practical significance in various spheres of human life: from mastering cultural patterns to professional performance of various forms of work. This situation emphasizes not only universality and accessibility, but also selection for quality education. A successful developing society requires competent, businesslike, competitive, enterprising people with highly qualified knowledge. All proposed priorities form the ultimate goals of research - the advancement of science to the world level and high demand for its results from the economy and society.

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